

Analytical Applications of 5-Ethylresacetophenone Oxime (5-ERAPO): Studies of Nickel Chelate

N. D. NAIK, H. B. NAIK* and C. M. DESAI**

Chemistry Department, S. V. R. College of Engineering, Surat-395001

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5-Ethylresacetophenone oxime (5-ERAPO) has been used as a reagent for gravimetric determination of nickel and for its separation from other ions. The precipitation of nickel by the reagent is complete at pH range from 6 to 10 and after drying at 110°-120°, the composition of the chelate corresponds to the formula $Ni(C_{10}H_{12}O_3N)_2$. Nickel has been determined gravimetrically in presence of some cations and anions.

THE well known reagents for gravimetric determination of nickel are dimethylglyoxime¹, nioxime², resacetophenone oxime³, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oxime⁴ etc. The purpose of the present investigation is to use new ligand 5-ERAPO^{5,6} for the gravimetric determination of nickel. The reagent precipitates nickel quantitatively at pH range 6 to 10. Cations like zinc(II), mercury(II), barium(II), calcium(II), strontium(II), magnesium(II) and anions like tartarate, citrate, chloride, nitrate are found not to interfere at pH range 7.0 to 7.5. Gravimetric determination of copper and nickel in their binary mixture has been carried out with satisfactory results taking advantage of the different pH range for precipitation.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Stock solutions of metal ions were prepared by dissolving pure salts in double distilled water and were employed after standardisation by standard methods⁷. Solutions of cations (0.05M) were used in all cases and the pH was adjusted using acetic acid and ammonium hydroxide buffer.

Reagent: 5-Ethylresacetophenone oxime (5-ERAPO)

4-Ethylresorcinol (7.5 g), obtained by the Clemmensen's reduction of resacetophenone, was heated with fused zinc chloride (20 g) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml). The reaction mixture was boiled and then cooled to room temperature. The reaction mixture was cooled with ice after the addition of 100 ml of 50% HCl. The product 5-ethylresacetophenone (5.2) was crystallised from hot benzene, m.p. 119°. Its oxime was prepared by usual method and crystallised from hot water, colourless crystals, m.p. 141°.

* Present address: Chemistry Department, Gujarat College, Ahmedabad-380006.

** Present address: P. T. Sarvajanic College of Science, Surat-395001.

Determination of nickel

A known volume of nickel solution taken in a beaker was diluted to about 200 ml and the pH was adjusted using acetic acid and ammonium hydroxide buffer. The solution was warmed to 60° and 1% ethanolic solution of the reagent was added with constant stirring till it was 10% excess over the calculated amount. The pale green precipitate of nickel chelate was digested on a water bath at about 60°-70° and allowed to stand for 30 min. It was filtered through a sintered glass crucible (G4), washed with hot water followed by 20% ethanol to remove excess reagent, dried at 110°-120° to constant weight and finally weighed as $Ni(C_{10}H_{12}O_3N)_2$. It has been found that nickel can be quantitatively determined at pH range 6.0 to 10.0, conversion factor for Ni(II) is 0.1314. Results of some of the estimations are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1. DETERMINATION OF NICKEL

(pH of the solution 7.5)

Ni(II) mg.	Ni(II) chelate obtained mg.	Ni(II) found mg.	Error mg.
7.32	56.0	7.36	+0.04
14.63	111.0	14.58	-0.05
21.96	167.0	21.95	-0.01
29.27	223.0	29.30	+0.03
36.59	278.0	36.53	-0.06
43.91	334.0	43.88	-0.03
58.56	446.0	58.60	+0.04

Determination of nickel in presence of foreign ions

To study the effect of foreign ions on gravimetric estimation of Ni(II), 50 mg. of various cations as well as anions were added to a known volume of nickel solution at pH 7.5 and estimation was carried out as mentioned above. It is observed that Zn(II),

Hg(II), Ba(II), Ca(II), Sr(II), Mg(II), tartarate, citrate, chloride, nitrate do not interfere in the estimation of nickel. Cobalt(II) gives orange chelate with the reagent and hence it interferes in the determination of nickel.

Separation and determination of copper and nickel :

Definite volumes of standard solutions of copper and nickel ions were mixed together and diluted to 200 ml. pH of solution was adjusted to 3.5 using acetate buffer. The buff coloured copper(II) chelate precipitated by adding ethanolic solution of 5-ERAPO was estimated gravimetrically⁶. The filtrate and washings after the removal of copper chelate were collected for the estimation of nickel. Its pH was adjusted to 7.5 and nickel was estimated with 5-ERAPO as above. Some of the results given in Table 2 show that copper and nickel can be accurately determined when present in the same solution.

On the basis of above results following structure is suggested for the nickel chelate.

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TABLE 2. ESTIMATION OF Cu(II) AND Ni(II)

Metal ion taken mg.		Chelate obtained mg.		Metal ion found mg.		Error mg.	
Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Ni(II)
7.85	7.32	55.0	56.0	7.74	7.36	-0.11	+0.04
15.71	29.27	111.0	223.0	15.75	29.30	+0.04	+0.03
31.43	14.63	224.0	111.0	31.50	14.58	+0.07	-0.05
31.43	29.27	224.0	223.0	31.50	29.30	+0.07	+0.03

Structure of nickel chelate

The nickel chelate was analysed for its carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen content to determine the composition. The metal content was determined by standard analytical method. [Found : C, 53.85; H, 5.25; N, 6.12; Ni, 13.08; Calc. C, 53.73, H, 5.37; N, 6.27; Ni, 13.14%]. The composition of chelate corresponds to the formula $Ni(C_{10}H_{12}O_3N)_2$ in which metal-ligand ratio is 1 : 2. The mol. wt. determined cryoscopically using camphor as solvent showed the chelate to be monomeric i.e., the chelate could be represented by ML_2 . The 1 : 2 stoichiometry is confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation. The nickel chelate is found to be a dimagnetic showing that it possesses a square planar structure.

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